

Stereo Anywhere: Robust Zero-Shot Deep Stereo Matching Even Where Either Stereo or Mono Fail

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<https://stereoanywhere.github.io/>

Figure 1. **Stereo Anywhere: Combining Monocular and Stereo Strengths for Robust Depth Estimation.** Our model achieves accurate results on standard conditions (on Middlebury [86]), while effectively handling non-Lambertian surfaces where stereo networks fail (on Booster [127]) and perspective illusions that deceive monocular depth foundation models (on MonoTrap, our novel dataset).

Abstract

We introduce *Stereo Anywhere*, a novel stereo-matching framework that combines geometric constraints with robust priors from monocular depth Vision Foundation Models (VFM). By elegantly coupling these complementary worlds through a dual-branch architecture, we seamlessly integrate stereo matching with learned contextual cues. Following this design, our framework introduces novel cost volume fusion mechanisms that effectively handle critical challenges such as textureless regions, occlusions, and non-Lambertian surfaces. Through our novel optical illusion dataset, *MonoTrap*, and extensive evaluation across multiple benchmarks, we demonstrate that our synthetic-only trained model achieves state-of-the-art results in zero-shot generalization, significantly outperforming existing solutions while showing remarkable robustness to challenging cases such as mirrors and transparencies.

1. Introduction

Stereo is a fundamental task that computes depth from a synchronized, rectified image pair by finding pixel correspondences to measure their horizontal offset (*disparity*). Due to its effectiveness and minimal hardware requirements, stereo has become prevalent in numerous applications, from autonomous navigation to augmented reality.

Although in principle single-image depth estimation [3] requires an even simpler acquisition setup, its ill-posed nature leads to scale ambiguity and perspective illusion issues that stereo methods inherently overcome through well-established geometric multi-view constraints.

However, despite significant advances through deep learning [47, 72], stereo models still face two main challenges: (i) limited generalization across different scenarios, and (ii) critical conditions that hinder matching or proper depth triangulation. Regarding (i), despite the initial success of synthetic datasets in enabling deep learn-

ing for stereo, their limited variety and simplified nature poorly reflect real-world complexity, and the scarcity of real training data further hinders the ability to handle heterogeneous scenarios. As for (ii), large textureless regions common in indoor environments make pixel matching highly ambiguous, while occlusions and non-Lambertian surfaces [76, 115, 127] violate the fundamental assumptions linking pixel correspondences to 3D geometry.

We argue that both challenges are rooted in the underlying limitations of stereo training data. Indeed, while data has scaled up to millions - or even billions - for several computer vision tasks, stereo datasets are still constrained in quantity and variety. This is particularly evident for non-Lambertian surfaces, which are severely underrepresented in existing datasets as their material properties prevent reliable depth measurements from active sensors (e.g. LiDAR).

In contrast, single-image depth estimation has recently witnessed a significant scale-up in data availability, reaching the order of *millions* of samples and enabling the emergence of Vision Foundation Models (VFMs) [22, 43, 120, 121]. Such data abundance has influenced these models in different ways, either through direct training on large-scale depth datasets [120, 121] or indirectly by leveraging networks pre-trained on *billions* of images for diverse tasks [22, 43]. Since these models rely on contextual cues for depth estimation, they show better capability in handling textureless regions and non-Lambertian materials [75, 81, 128, 129] while being inherently immune to occlusions. Modern graphics engines have further accelerated this progress, enabling rapid generation of high-quality synthetic data with dense depth annotations. However, although synthetic datasets featuring non-Lambertian surfaces like HyperSim [81] have proven effective for monocular depth estimation [75, 128, 129], this data abundance has not translated to stereo. Despite efforts in generating stereo pairs via novel view synthesis [24, 54, 104], available data remains insufficient for robust stereo matching.

In this paper, rather than focusing on costly real-world data collection or generating additional synthetic datasets, we propose to bridge this gap by leveraging existing VFMs for single-view depth estimation. To this end, we develop a novel dual-branch deep architecture that combines stereo matching principles with monocular depth cues. Specifically, while one branch of the proposed network constructs a cost volume from learned stereo image features, the other branch processes depth predictions from the VFM on both left and right images to build a second cost volume that incorporates depth priors to guide the disparity estimation process. These complementary signals are then iteratively combined [55], along with novel augmentation strategies applied to both cost volumes, to predict the final disparity map. Through this design, our network achieves robust performance on challenging cases like textureless re-

gions, occlusions, and non-Lambertian surfaces, while requiring minimal synthetic stereo data. Importantly, while leveraging monocular cues, our approach preserves stereo matching geometric guarantees, effectively handling scenarios where monocular depth estimation typically fails, such as in the presence of perspective illusions. We validate this through our novel dataset of optical illusions, comprising 26 scenes with ground-truth depth maps.

We dub our framework *Stereo Anywhere*, highlighting its ability to overcome the individual limitations of stereo and monocular approaches, as depicted in Fig. 1. To summarize, our main contributions are:

- A novel deep stereo architecture leveraging monocular depth VFMs to achieve strong generalization capabilities and robustness to challenging conditions.
- Novel data augmentation strategies designed to enhance the robustness of our model to textureless regions and non-Lambertian surfaces.
- A challenging dataset with optical illusion, which is particularly challenging for monocular depth with VFMs.
- Extensive experiments showing Stereo Anywhere’s superior generalization and robustness to conditions critical for either stereo or monocular approaches.

2. Related Works

We briefly review the literature relevant to our work.

Deep Stereo Matching. In the last decade, stereo matching has transitioned from classical hand-crafted algorithms [85] to deep learning solutions, leading to unprecedented accuracy in depth estimation. Early deep learning efforts focused on replacing individual components of the conventional pipeline [88, 96, 105, 130, 131]. Since DispNetC [61], end-to-end architectures have evolved into 2D [53, 92, 125, 125] and 3D [4, 8, 9, 32, 44, 90, 91, 119, 132, 134] approaches, processing cost volumes through correlation layers or 3D convolutions respectively. More recent advances, thoroughly reviewed in [47, 72, 107], include recurrent architectures for stereo matching [13, 27, 40, 50, 55, 110, 116, 140] inspired by RAFT [99], Transformer-based solutions [31, 52, 59, 97, 113, 117, 138] for capturing long-range dependencies, and fully data-driven MRF models [28]. Among them, some methods specifically address temporal consistency in stereo videos [41, 42, 133, 137]. Domain generalization remains a major challenge, with various approaches proposed including domain-invariant feature learning [17, 56, 80, 93, 135], hand-crafted matching costs [7, 15], integration of additional geometric cues [2, 66, 105], and exploitation of sparse depth measurements from active sensors [5, 49, 69]. In parallel, self-supervised approaches [25, 57] have emerged as effective alternatives to supervised learning, even using pseudo-labels from traditional algorithms [1, 100] or deploying neural radiance fields [104]. Despite the numerous attempts to

Figure 2. **Stereo Anywhere Architecture.** Given a stereo pair, (1) a pre-trained backbone is used to extract features and then build a correlation volume. Such a volume is then truncated (2) to reject matching costs computed for disparity hypotheses being *behind* non-Lambertian surfaces – glasses and mirrors. On a parallel branch, the two images are processed by a monocular VFM to obtain two depth maps (3): these are used to build a second correlation volume from retrieved normals (4). This volume is then aggregated through a 3D CNN to predict a new disparity map, used to align the original monocular depth to metric scale through a differentiable scaling module (5) for it. In parallel, the monocular depth map from left images is processed by another backbone (6) to extract context features. Finally, the two volumes and the context features from monocular depth guide the iterative disparity prediction (7).

improve specific aspects through the aforementioned techniques, recent architectures achieve remarkable generalization by combining their architectural advances with the increasing availability of diverse training data, while online adaptation techniques enable further improvements during deployment through self-supervised learning [45, 67, 71, 101]. However, although progress on challenges like over-smoothing [103, 118] and visually imbalanced stereo [2, 11, 58, 105], handling non-Lambertian surfaces remains particularly challenging due to limited annotated data and complex appearance, with rare works like Depth4ToM [18] specifically addressing this through semantic guidance. Among all the aforementioned approaches, there have been limited attempts to integrate stereo with monocular cues [1, 12, 112], mostly in self-supervised settings or through loose coupling between modalities.

Monocular Depth Estimation. Parallel to developments in stereo matching, single-image depth estimation has evolved from hand-crafted features [82] to deep learning methods [10, 21, 48, 73, 108], with self-supervised approaches [25, 26, 60, 68, 111, 139, 141] reframing the task as an image reconstruction problem. This led to multi-task approaches incorporating flow [79, 102, 124, 142] and semantics [29, 126], alongside advances in uncertainty estimation [34, 70] and dynamic object handling [46, 63, 98]. Affine-invariant models [20, 77, 78, 109, 122] marked a breakthrough in cross-domain generalization, pioneered by MiDaS [78] and followed by works like DPT [77] and, more recently, the Depth Anything series [120]. These approaches used different data sources, from internet photos [51, 94, 95, 122] to car sensors [23, 62] and RGB-D devices [16, 64], representing the first generation of VFMs for

monocular depth estimation. Recent works have focused on metric depth estimation through camera parameter integration [30, 35, 123], diffusion models [19, 22, 33, 38, 43, 83, 84], and temporal consistency [36, 89]. Moreover, material-aware methods [18], diffusion models [106], and large-scale synthetic datasets have enabled robust monocular depth estimation for non-Lambertian surfaces [121]. Stereo methods, however, still struggle with these surfaces due to limited real-world and synthetic annotated data, affecting generalization. We address this by integrating robust monocular VFMs into a stereo architecture.

Concurrent Works. Finally, we mention some solutions for stereo [14, 39, 114] and for multi-view stereo [37], developed in parallel with ours and sharing similar rationale.

3. Method Overview

Given a rectified stereo pair $\mathbf{I}_L, \mathbf{I}_R \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times H \times W}$, we first obtain monocular depth estimates (MDEs) $\mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_R \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times H \times W}$ using a generic VFM ϕ_M for monocular depth estimation. We aim to estimate a disparity map $\mathbf{D} = \phi_S(\mathbf{I}_L, \mathbf{I}_R, \mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_R)$, incorporating VFM priors to provide accurate results even under challenging conditions, such as texture-less areas, occlusions, and non-Lambertian surfaces. At the same time, our stereo network ϕ_S is designed to avoid depth estimation errors that could arise from relying solely on contextual cues, which can be ambiguous, like in the presence of visual illusions.

Following recent advances in iterative models [55], Stereo Anywhere comprises three main stages, as shown in Fig. 2: I) Feature Extraction, II) Correlation Pyramids Building, and III) Iterative Disparity Estimation.

3.1. Feature Extraction

Two distinct types of features are extracted [55]: image features and context features – (1) and (6) in Fig. 2. The image features are obtained through a feature encoder processing the stereo pair, yielding feature maps $\mathbf{F}_L, \mathbf{F}_R \in \mathbb{R}^{D \times \frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}}$, which are used to build a stereo correlation volume at $\frac{1}{4}$ of the original input resolution. These encoders are initialized with pre-trained weights [55] and the image encoder is kept frozen during training. For context features, we employ a context encoder with identical architecture to the feature encoder, but processing the monocular depth estimate aligned with the reference image \mathbf{M}_L – (3) in Fig. 2 – instead of \mathbf{I}_L to capture strong geometry priors. Accordingly, during training the context encoder is optimized to extract meaningful features from these depth maps.

3.2. Correlation Pyramids Building

As a standard practice in stereo matching, the *cost volume* is the data structure encoding the similarity between pixels across two images. Accordingly, our model utilizes cost volumes—specifically Correlation Pyramids [55]—but in a novel manner. Indeed, Stereo Anywhere constructs two correlation pyramids: a *stereo correlation volume* derived from $\mathbf{I}_L, \mathbf{I}_R$ to encode image similarities, and a *monocular correlation volume* from $\mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_R$ to encode geometric similarities—(2) and (4) in Fig. 2. Unlike the former, the latter remains unaffected by non-Lambertian surfaces, assuming a robust ϕ_M .

Stereo Correlation Volume. Given $\mathbf{F}_L, \mathbf{F}_R$, we construct a 3D correlation volume \mathbf{V}_S using dot product between feature maps:

$$(\mathbf{V}_S)_{ijk} = \sum_h (\mathbf{F}_L)_{hij} \cdot (\mathbf{F}_R)_{hik}, \quad \mathbf{V}_S \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}} \quad (1)$$

Monocular Correlation Volume. Given $\mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_R$, we downsample them to $1/4$, compute their normals ∇_L, ∇_R , and construct a 3D correlation volume \mathbf{V}_M using dot product between normal maps:

$$(\mathbf{V}_M)_{ijk} = \sum_h (\nabla_L)_{hij} \cdot (\nabla_R)_{hik}, \quad \mathbf{V}_M \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}} \quad (2)$$

Given the absence of texture in ∇_L and ∇_R , the resulting monocular volume \mathbf{V}_M will be less informative. To alleviate this problem we segment \mathbf{V}_M using the relative depth priors from \mathbf{M}_L and \mathbf{M}_R : to do so, we generate left and right segmentation masks $\mathcal{M}_L \in \{0, 1\}^{\frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4} \times 1}$, $\mathcal{M}_R \in \{0, 1\}^{\frac{H}{4} \times 1 \times \frac{W}{4}}$. We refer the reader to the **supplementary material** for a detailed description. Given the segmentation masks, we can generate masked volumes as:

$$(\mathbf{V}_M^n)_{ijk} = (\mathcal{M}_L^n)_{ij} \cdot (\mathcal{M}_R^n)_{ik} \cdot (\mathbf{V}_M)_{ijk} \quad (3)$$

Next, we insert a 3D Convolutional Regularization module ϕ_A to aggregate \mathbf{V}_M^n , resulting in $\mathbf{V}'_M = \phi_A(\mathbf{V}_M^1, \dots, \mathbf{V}_M^N, \mathbf{M}_L, \mathbf{M}_R)$, with $N = 8$. The architecture of ϕ_A follows the one in [116], with a simple permutation to match the structure of the correlation volumes. We propose an adapted version of CoEx [4] correlation volume excitation that exploits both views. The resulting feature volumes $\mathbf{V}'_M \in \mathbb{R}^{F \times \frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}}$ are fed to two different shallow 3D conv layers ϕ_D and ϕ_C to obtain two aggregated volumes $\mathbf{V}_M^D = \phi_D(\mathbf{V}'_M)$ and $\mathbf{V}_M^C = \phi_C(\mathbf{V}'_M)$ with $\mathbf{V}_M^D, \mathbf{V}_M^C \in \mathbb{R}^{\frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}}$.

Differentiable Monocular Scaling. Volume \mathbf{V}_M^D will be used not only as a monocular guide for the iterative refinement unit but also to estimate the coarse disparity maps $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{D}}_R$, while \mathbf{V}_M^C is used to estimate confidence maps $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{C}}_R$. These maps are then used to scale both \mathbf{M}_L and \mathbf{M}_R – (5) in Fig. 2. To estimate left disparity from a correlation volume, we first perform a *softargmax* on the last W dimension of \mathbf{V}_M^D to extract the correlated pixel x-coordinate. Then, given the relationship between left disparity and correlation $d_L = j_L - j_R$, we obtain a coarse disparity map $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_L$:

$$(\hat{\mathbf{D}}_L)_{ij} = j - (\text{softargmax}_L(\mathbf{V}_M^D))_{ij} \quad (4)$$

Similarly, we estimate $\hat{\mathbf{D}}_R$ from \mathbf{V}_M^D . We refer the reader to the supplementary for details. We also estimate a pair of confidence maps $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{C}}_R \in [0, 1]^{H \times W}$ to classify outliers and perform robust scaling. Inspired by information entropy, we measure the *chaos* within correlation curves: clear monomodal-like cost curves—those with low entropy—are reliable, while *chaotic* curves with high entropy indicate uncertainty. To estimate the left confidence map, we perform a *softmax* operation on the last W dimension of \mathbf{V}_M^C , then $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_L$ is obtained as follows:

$$(\hat{\mathbf{C}}_L)_{ij} = 1 + \frac{\sum_d \frac{W}{4} \frac{e^{(\mathbf{V}_M^C)_{ijd}}}{\sum_f \frac{W}{4} e^{(\mathbf{V}_M^C)_{ijf}}}}{\log_2\left(\frac{e^{(\mathbf{V}_M^C)_{ijd}}}{\sum_f \frac{W}{4} e^{(\mathbf{V}_M^C)_{ijf}}}\right)} \quad (5)$$

In the same way, we estimate $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_R$. To further reduce outliers, we mask out occluded pixels from $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_L$ and $\hat{\mathbf{C}}_R$ using a *SoftLRC* operator – see the **supplementary material** for details. Finally, we estimate the scale \hat{s} and shift \hat{t} using a differentiable weighted least-square approach:

$$\min_{\hat{s}, \hat{t}} \sum_{L,R} \left\| \sqrt{\hat{\mathbf{C}}} \odot [(\hat{s}\mathbf{M} + \hat{t}) - \hat{\mathbf{D}}] \right\|_F \quad (6)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_F$ denotes the Frobenius norm. Using the scaling coefficients, we obtain two disparity maps $\hat{\mathbf{M}}_L, \hat{\mathbf{M}}_R$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{M}}_L = \hat{s}\mathbf{M}_L + \hat{t}, \quad \hat{\mathbf{M}}_R = \hat{s}\mathbf{M}_R + \hat{t} \quad (7)$$

Figure 3. **Samples from MonoTrap Dataset.** We report two scenes featured in our dataset, showing the left image, the ground-truth depth, and the predictions by Depth Anything v2 [121], highlighting how it fails in the presence of visual illusions.

It is crucial to optimize both left and right scaling jointly to obtain consistency between \hat{M}_L and \hat{M}_R .

Volume Augmentations. Unfortunately, Stereo Anywhere cannot properly learn when to choose stereo or mono information from [61] alone. Hence, we propose three volume augmentations and a monocular augmentation to overcome this issue: 1) *Volume Rolling*: we randomly apply a rolling operation to the last W dimension of \mathbf{V}_M^D or \mathbf{V}_S ; 2) *Volume Noising*: we apply random noise sampled from the interval $[0, 1)$ using a uniform distribution; 3) *Volume Zeroing*: we apply a Gaussian-like curve with the peak where disparity equals zero. Furthermore, we randomly substitute the monocular depth with ground truth normalized between $[0, 1]$ as an additional augmentation. We apply only one volume augmentation to \mathbf{V}_M^D or \mathbf{V}_S and only for a section of the volume, randomly selecting an \mathcal{M}_L^n mask.

Volume Truncation. To further help Stereo Anywhere to handle mirror surfaces, we introduce a hand-crafted volume truncation operation on \mathbf{V}_S . Firstly, we extract left confidence $\mathbf{C}_M = \text{softLRC}_L(\hat{M}_L, \hat{M}_R)$ to classify reliable monocular predictions. Then, we create a truncate mask $\mathbf{T} \in [0, 1]^{\frac{H}{4} \times \frac{W}{4}}$ using the following logic condition: $(\mathbf{T})_{ij} = \left[\left((\hat{M}_L)_{ij} > (\hat{D}_L)_{ij} \right) \wedge (\mathbf{C}_M)_{ij} \right] \vee \left[(\mathbf{C}_M)_{ij} \wedge \neg(\hat{C}_L)_{ij} \right]$. We implement this logic using fuzzy operators (more details in the **supplementary material**). The rationale is that stereo predicts farther depths on mirror surfaces: the mirror is perceived as a window into a new environment, specular to the real one. Finally, for values of $\mathbf{T} > T_m = 0.98$, we truncate \mathbf{V}_S using a sigmoid curve centered at the correlation value predicted by \hat{M}_L – *i.e.*, the real disparity of mirror surfaces – preserving only the stereo correlation curve not “piercing” mirrors.

3.3. Iterative Disparity Estimation

We aim to estimate a series of refined disparity maps $\{\mathbf{D}^1 = \hat{M}_L, \mathbf{D}^2, \dots, \mathbf{D}^l, \dots\}$ exploiting the guidance from both stereo and mono branches. Starting from the Multi-GRU update operator by [55], we introduce a second lookup operator that extracts correlation features \mathbf{G}_M from the additional volume \mathbf{V}_M^D – (7) in Fig. 2. The two sets of correlation features from \mathbf{G}_S and \mathbf{G}_M are processed by the same two-layer encoder and concatenated with features derived from the current disparity estimation \mathbf{D}^l . This concatena-

tion is further processed by a 2D conv layer, and then by the ConvGRU operator. We inherit the convex upsampling module [55] to upsample final disparity to full resolution.

3.4. Training Supervision

We supervise the iterative module using the well-known L1 loss with exponentially increasing weights [55], then \hat{D}_L , \hat{D}_R , \hat{M}_L and \hat{M}_R using the L1 loss, finally \hat{C}_L and \hat{C}_R using the Binary Cross Entropy loss. We invite the reader to read the **supplementary material** for additional details.

4. The MonoTrap Dataset

Monocular depth estimation is known for possibly failing in the presence of perspective illusions. The reader may wonder how Stereo Anywhere would behave in such cases: would it blindly trust the monocular VFM or rely on the stereo geometric principles to maintain robustness?

To answer these questions, we introduce MonoTrap, a novel stereo dataset specifically designed to challenge monocular depth estimation. Our dataset comprises 26 scenes featuring perspective illusions, captured with a calibrated stereo setup and annotated with ground-truth depth from an Intel Realsense L515 LiDAR. The scenes contain carefully designed planar patterns that create visual illusions, such as apparent holes in walls or floors and simulated transparent surfaces that reveal content behind them. Figure 3 shows examples from our dataset that illustrate how these visual illusions easily fool monocular methods.

5. Experiments

We describe our implementation details, datasets, and evaluation protocols, followed by experiments. We also refer the reader to the **supplementary material** for more results.

5.1. Implementation and Experimental Settings

We implement Stereo Anywhere using PyTorch, starting from RAFT-Stereo codebase [55]. We use Depth Anything v2 [121] as the VFM fueling our model, using the *Large* weights provided by the authors, trained on ground-truth labels from the HyperSim synthetic dataset [81] only.

Starting from the SceneFlow RAFT-Stereo checkpoint, we train Stereo Anywhere on a single A100 GPU for 3 epochs, with learning rate $1e-4$ and AdamW optimizer, on

Experiment	Booster (Q)					Middlebury 2014 (H)			
	bad					All	bad > 2		Avg. (px)
	> 2	> 4	> 6	> 8	Noc		Occ		
(A) Baseline [55]	17.84	13.06	10.76	9.24	3.59	11.15	8.06	29.06	1.55
(B) (A) + Monocular Context w/o re-train	15.85	10.98	8.89	7.69	3.05	14.96	11.70	34.38	2.82
(C) (A) + Monocular Context w/ re-train	14.94	10.40	8.61	7.63	3.03	9.62	6.98	25.39	1.13
(D) (C) + Normals Correlation Volume / Scaled Depth	11.33	6.88	5.32	4.59	1.87	7.67	5.24	21.51	0.96
(E) (D) + Volume augmentation / truncation	9.01	5.40	4.12	3.34	1.21	6.96	4.75	20.34	0.94

Table 1. **Ablation Studies.** We measure the impact of different design strategies. Networks trained on SceneFlow [61].

Model	Middlebury 2014 (H)				Middlebury 2021				ETH3D				KITTI 2012				KITTI 2015			
	bad > 2				bad > 2				bad > 1				bad > 3				bad > 3			
	All	Noc	Occ	Avg. (px)	All	Noc	Occ	Avg. (px)	All	Noc	Occ	Avg. (px)	All	Noc	Occ	Avg. (px)	All	Noc	Occ	Avg. (px)
RAFT-Stereo [55]	11.15	8.06	29.06	1.55	12.05	9.38	37.89	1.81	2.59	2.24	8.78	0.25	4.80	4.23	29.21	0.89	5.44	5.21	14.09	1.16
PSMNet [8]	18.79	13.80	53.22	4.63	23.67	20.61	53.75	5.70	19.75	18.62	42.05	0.94	6.73	5.81	46.24	1.22	6.78	6.40	24.85	1.38
GMSTereo [117]	15.63	10.98	46.04	1.87	25.43	22.43	54.70	2.86	6.22	5.58	19.97	0.42	5.68	4.87	38.84	1.10	5.72	5.44	17.33	1.21
ELFNet [59]	24.48	16.94	77.06	8.61	27.08	21.77	85.56	11.01	25.61	24.50	46.06	5.65	10.52	8.67	88.21	2.30	9.61	8.22	85.64	2.16
PCVNet [132]	16.79	13.54	35.66	2.96	12.92	10.19	40.23	2.18	4.24	3.61	14.01	0.41	4.44	3.92	27.70	0.89	5.08	4.88	13.72	1.24
DLNR [140]	9.46	6.20	28.75	1.45	8.44	5.88	32.71	1.24	23.12	22.94	26.93	9.89	9.45	8.83	36.75	1.59	15.74	15.41	34.32	2.83
Selective-RAFT [110]	12.05	9.46	27.42	2.35	15.69	13.86	36.32	5.92	4.36	3.81	10.23	0.34	5.71	5.16	30.54	1.08	6.50	6.22	18.44	1.27
Selective-IGEV [110]	9.98	7.09	27.62	1.60	8.89	6.34	32.88	1.60	6.42	5.71	18.71	1.73	6.22	5.54	34.78	1.09	5.87	5.66	14.99	1.42
IGEV-Stereo [116]	9.91	7.08	26.26	1.84	9.15	6.43	34.88	1.53	4.30	3.86	12.65	0.38	5.65	4.43	33.38	1.03	5.87	5.13	14.31	1.34
NMRF [28]	14.08	10.87	34.62	2.91	23.36	21.69	42.51	8.57	4.34	3.66	17.15	0.42	4.62	4.05	30.65	0.92	5.24	5.07	12.28	1.16
Stereo Anywhere (ours)	6.96	4.75	20.34	0.94	7.97	5.71	29.52	1.08	1.66	1.43	5.29	0.24	3.90	3.52	21.65	0.83	3.93	3.79	11.01	0.97

Table 2. **Zero-shot Generalization.** Comparison with state-of-the-art deep stereo models. Networks trained on SceneFlow [61].

batches of 2 images. We extract random crops of size 320×640 from images and apply standard color and spatial augmentations [55]. The VFM is used only to source monocular depth maps, remaining frozen during training.

The number of iterations for GRUs is fixed to 12 during training and increased to 32 at inference time.

5.2. Evaluation Datasets & Protocol

Datasets. We utilize SceneFlow [61] as our sole training dataset, comprising about 39k synthetic stereo pairs with dense ground-truth disparities. For evaluation, we employ several benchmarks: Middlebury 2014 [86] and its 2021 extension [65] provide high-resolution indoor scenes with semi-dense labels (15 and 24 stereo pairs), KITTI 2012 [23] and 2015 [62] feature outdoor driving scenarios (~ 200 pairs each at 1280×384 with sparse LiDAR ground truth), and ETH3D [87] contributes 27 low-resolution indoor/outdoor scenes. For non-Lambertian surfaces, we primarily use Booster [127], containing 228 high-resolution (12 Mpx) indoor pairs with its 191-pair online benchmark, and LayeredFlow [115], featuring 400 pairs with transparent objects and sparse ground truth (~ 50 points per pair). Additionally, we include our newly proposed MonoTrap dataset focusing on optical illusions. For zero-shot evaluation, we test on KITTI 2015, Middlebury v3 at half (H) resolution, Middlebury 2021, and ETH3D, while non-Lambertian zero-shot testing relies on Booster at quarter (Q) resolution and LayeredFlow at eight (E) resolution.

Evaluation Metrics. We evaluate our method using two standard metrics: the average pixel error (Avg.), which computes the absolute difference between predicted and ground truth disparities averaged over all pixels, and the $\text{bad} > \tau$ error, which measures the percentage of pixels with a disparity error greater than τ pixels – for the latter, we compute it considering all pixels or either non-occluded or

occluded pixels, referred to as *All*, *Noc* or *Occ* respectively.

We evaluate on MonoTrap through standard monocular depth metrics [25] - Absolute relative error (AbsRel), RMSE, and $\delta < 1.05$ score.

5.3. Ablation Study

We start our analysis by evaluating how individual components of our model contribute to the overall accuracy. All model variants are trained solely on the synthetic SceneFlow dataset and tested on Booster and Middlebury 2014, allowing us to examine their effectiveness on non-Lambertian surfaces and general scenes.

Table 1 summarizes our findings. In (A), we report the performance of our baseline model, upon which we build Stereo Anywhere – i.e., RAFT-stereo [55]. On the one hand, by adding monocular context from an off-the-shelf monocular depth network to the pre-trained context backbone (B), we observe improved performance on non-Lambertian surfaces, though at the expense of a general drop in accuracy on Middlebury. On the other hand, by re-training the context backbone to process depth maps obtained from the monocular network on SceneFlow (C), we can appreciate a consistent improvement in both datasets. Introducing the normals correlation volume with subsequent differentiable depth scaling (D) significantly enhances the accuracy on non-Lambertian surfaces, also showing improvements on indoor scenes. Finally, cost volume augmentations and truncation (E) demonstrate positive effects on transparent surfaces and mirrors present in the Booster dataset by further reducing the bad-2 metric by approximately 1.5% and Avg. by 0.7 pixels, with minimal influence on Middlebury.

According to these results, from now on, we will adopt (E) as the default setting for Stereo Anywhere.

Figure 4. **Qualitative Results – Zero-Shot Generalization.** Predictions by state-of-the-art models and Stereo Anywhere.

Model	Booster (Q)					Avg. (px)	LayeredFlow (E)			
	Error Rate (%)				Avg. (px)		Error Rate (%)			Avg. (px)
	> 2	> 4	> 6	> 8			> 1	> 3	> 5	
RAFT-Stereo [55]	17.84	13.06	10.76	9.24	3.59	89.21	79.02	71.61	19.27	
PSMNet [8]	34.47	24.83	20.46	17.77	7.26	91.85	79.84	70.04	21.18	
GMStereo [117]	32.44	22.52	17.96	15.02	5.29	92.95	83.68	74.76	20.91	
ELFNet [59]	45.52	35.79	30.72	27.33	14.04	93.08	82.24	70.41	20.19	
PCVNet [132]	22.63	16.51	13.81	12.08	4.70	88.27	76.65	66.79	18.19	
DLNR [140]	18.56	14.55	12.61	11.22	3.97	89.90	79.46	72.72	18.97	
Selective-RAFT [110]	20.01	15.08	12.52	10.88	4.12	92.69	86.32	78.82	20.18	
Selective-IGEV [110]	18.52	14.24	12.14	10.77	4.38	91.31	81.72	74.74	19.65	
IGEV-Stereo [116]	16.90	13.23	11.40	10.20	3.94	87.28	80.07	72.91	19.07	
NMRF [28]	27.08	19.06	15.43	13.21	5.02	89.08	79.13	70.51	20.17	
Stereo Anywhere (ours)	9.01	5.40	4.12	3.34	1.21	81.83	57.66	45.12	11.20	

Model	Booster (Q) Online Benchmark				Avg. (px)	LayeredFlow (E)			
	> 2	> 4	> 6	> 8		> 1	> 3	> 5	
DKT-RAFT [136] (*)	10.32	7.13	5.65	4.36	1.70	66.05	46.95	37.77	8.72
Stereo Anywhere (ours) (*)	6.52	2.82	1.77	1.27	0.73	51.24	25.63	15.65	4.84

Table 3. **Zero-shot Non-Lambertian Generalization.** Comparison with state-of-the-art models. Networks trained on SceneFlow [61]. (*) means fine-tuned on Booster training set.

5.4. Zero-Shot Generalization

We now compare our Stereo Anywhere model against state-of-the-art deep stereo networks, assessing zero-shot generalization capability when transferred from synthetic to real images. Purposely, we follow a well-established benchmark in the literature [55, 104], evaluating on real datasets models pre-trained exclusively on SceneFlow [61].

Table 2 compares Stereo Anywhere with off-the-shelf stereo networks using authors’ provided weights. Considering All, Noc, and Avg. metrics, we can notice how Stereo Anywhere achieves consistently better results across most datasets, achieving almost 3% lower bad-2 All on Middlebury 2014 versus the second-best method DLNR [140], and breaking the 4% barrier on KITTI’s bad-3 All metric.

The Occ metric further demonstrates how Stereo Anywhere consistently outperforms other stereo models on any dataset, with substantial margins over the second-best – i.e., approximately 6% on Middlebury 2014 and KITTI 2012, and 3% on ETH3D. This confirms that leveraging priors from VFMs for monocular depth estimation effectively improve the stereo matching estimation accuracy in challenging conditions where stereo matching is ill-posed, such as

at occluded regions.

Figure 4 shows predictions on KITTI 2015, Middlebury 2014, and ETH3D samples. In particular, the first row shows an extremely challenging case for SceneFlow-trained models, where Stereo Anywhere achieves accurate disparity maps thanks to VFM priors.

5.5. Zero-Shot Non-Lambertian Generalization

We now assess the generalization capabilities of Stereo Anywhere and existing stereo models when dealing with non-Lambertian materials, such as transparent surfaces or mirrors. To this end, we conduct a zero-shot generalization evaluation experiment on the Booster [74] and LayeredFlow [115] datasets, once again using models pre-trained on SceneFlow [61] – with weights provided by the authors.

Table 3 shows the outcome of this evaluation. This time, we can perceive even more clearly how Stereo Anywhere is the absolute winner, demonstrating unprecedented robustness in the presence of non-Lambertian surfaces despite being trained only on synthetic stereo data, not even featuring such objects. These results further validate how leveraging strong priors from existing VFMs for monocular depth esti-

Figure 5. **Qualitative results – Zero-Shot non-Lambertian Generalization.** Predictions by state-of-the-art models and Stereo Anywhere.

Model	MonoTrap		
	AbsRel (%)↓	RMSE (m)↓	$\sigma < 1.05$ (%)↑
Depth Anything v2 [121]	53.46	0.36	15.21
Depth Anything v2 [121] †	27.92	0.27	19.43
DepthPro [6]	47.77	0.32	21.90
DepthPro [6] †	20.82	0.22	22.88
RAFT-Stereo [55]	5.01	0.09	77.05
Stereo Anywhere	3.50	0.06	80.27

Table 4. **MonoTrap Benchmark.** Comparison with state-of-the-art monocular depth estimation models and RAFT-Stereo. Both RAFT-Stereo and Stereo Anywhere are trained on SceneFlow [61]. † refers to robust scaling through RANSAC.

mation can play a game-changing role in stereo matching as well, especially when lacking training data explicitly targeting critical conditions such as non-Lambertian surfaces. At the bottom, we report results achieved by fine-tuning Stereo Anywhere on the Booster training set and evaluating on the online benchmark. Our model ranks first when evaluated at quarter resolution.

Figure 5 shows examples from Booster and LayeredFlow, where Stereo Anywhere is the only stereo model correctly perceiving the mirror and transparent railing.

5.6. MonoTrap Benchmark

We conclude our evaluation by running experiments on our newly collected MonoTrap dataset to prove the robustness of Stereo Anywhere in the presence of critical conditions harming the accuracy of monocular depth predictors.

Table 4 collects the results achieved by state-of-the-art monocular depth estimation models, the baseline stereo model over which we built our framework (RAFT-Stereo) and Stereo Anywhere. Regarding the former models, as they predict affine-invariant depth maps, following the literature [78] we use least square errors to align them to the ground-truth. As these models are fooled by the visual illusions, this scaling procedure is likely to yield sub-optimal scale and shift parameters. Therefore, we alternatively align to ground-truth depth through a more robust RANSAC fitting – denoted with † in the table.

On the one hand, by comparing monocular and stereo methods, we notice how the failures of the former negatively impact their evaluation metrics. Once again, we re-

Figure 6. **Qualitative results – MonoTrap.** Stereo Anywhere is not fooled by erroneous predictions by its monocular engine [121].

mark that a direct comparison across the two families of methods is not the main goal of this experiment. On the other hand, we focus on the comparison between RAFT-Stereo and Stereo Anywhere, with our model performing slightly better than its baseline. This fact proves that despite its strong reliance on the priors retrieved from VFMs for monocular depth estimation, Stereo Anywhere can properly ignore such priors when unreliable.

Figure 6 shows three samples where Depth Anything v2 fails while Stereo Anywhere does not.

6. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduced Stereo Anywhere, a novel stereo matching framework that leverages monocular depth VFMs to overcome traditional stereo matching limitations. Combining stereo geometric constraints with monocular priors, our approach demonstrates superior zero-shot generalization and robustness to challenging conditions like textureless regions, occlusions, and non-Lambertian surfaces. Furthermore, through our novel MonoTrap dataset, we showed that Stereo Anywhere effectively combines the best of both worlds - maintaining stereo matching’s geometric accuracy where monocular methods fail, while leveraging monocular priors to handle challenging stereo scenarios. Extensive comparisons against state-of-the-art networks in zero-shot settings validate these findings.

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